

TILSHUNOSLIK FANINING KICHIK BO'LIMLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslikning kichik bo'limlariga kiruvchi terminologiya, onomastika, paremiologiya, frazeologiya, etimologiya haqida ma'lumot berib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: termin, sheva, lahja, ibora, atama.

1. Terminologiya. Ma'lum bir fan yoki kasb-hunar muayyan bir tushunchani aniq ifodalash uchun ma'nosi maxsuslashtirilgan so'z yoki so'z birikmalariga atama(termin) deyiladi. Atamalar qo'llanishiga ko'ra 2 ga bo'linadi:

a) kasbiy atamalar-ma'lum kasb-hunar doirasida aniq bir ma'noni ifodalash uchun qo'llaniladigan so'zlar. Masalan: angor, loya, qolip, sog'i

b) ilmiy terminlar – ma'lum bir fan doirasida qo'llaniladigan atamalar. Masalan: aruz nazariyasida hazaj, ramal, mutaqorib.

Atamalar asosan, 2 yo'l bilan hosil bo'ladi:

a) umumxalq tilidagi ayrim so'zlarning ma'nosini maxsuslashtirib olish orqali.

Bunday so'zlar umumxalq tilida bir ma'noda fan tilida boshqa bir ma'noda ishlatiladi. Masalan: ega so'zi umumxalq tilida biror narsaning sohibi ma'nosida ishlatiladi. Fan tilida esa bosh bo'laklarning biri sifatida qo'llaniladi

b) boshqa tillarda atamalar uchun maxsus so'zlar qabul qilish orqali. Bunday so'zlar umumxalq tilida ishlatilmaydi, faqat atama sifatida qo'llaniladi. Masalan: kasr, musbat, manfiy, fonema.

Atamalarni yaratish tamoyillari, ularni tartibga solish bilan shug'ullanuvchi tilshunoslikning maxsus bo'limi borki, bunday bo'lim atamashunoslik(terminologiya) deb nomlanadi. Hozirgi atamashunosligimizning bosh tamoyili:

a) atamalarni mumkin qadar milliy lashtirish, tilimizning ichki imkoniyatlari asosida atamalar yaratish. Masalan: kichik korxonalar, qo'shma korxonalar

b) zarur hollarda yangi tushunchalarni ifodalovchi chet tilidan kirib kelgan atamalarni qabul qilish. Masalan: kompaniya, fermer, dizayn.

2. Onomastika. Nomlar va ularning turlari, nomlanish sabablari bilan shug'ullanuvchi tilshunoslikning bo'limi. Onomastika tarkibida:

a) antroponimlar – shaxs va ularga qo'yilgan nomlar

b) toponimlar – geografik obyektlar va ularga qo'yilgan nomlari

d) zoonimlar – hayvon nomlari, ularga atab qo'yilgan nomlar

e) gidronimlar – suv havzalari inshootlari, ularga atab qo'yilgan nomlar o'rganiladi.

O'zbek onomastikasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishida professor Ernest Begmatov katta hissa qo'shgan. Uning "Kishi nomlari imlosi", "O'zbek ismlar imlosi", 14600 ismning izohini o'z ichiga olgan "O'zbek ismlari" kitoblari alohida qimmatga ega.

3. Dialektologiya. Faqat ma'lum bir hudud doirasidagina qo'llanilib, boshqa hududda yashovchi o'zbek tili vakillari uchun xos bo'lmagan so'zlar hududiy chegaralangan (shevaga xos) so'zlar yoki dialektalizmlar deb nomlanadi.

Masalan: eshik (Andijon) – hovli, uy

Shoti (Farg'ona) – narvon

Shevaga xos so'zlar dialektologiya (shevashunoslik) bo'limida o'rganiladi. Shevaga xos so'zlar adabiy tildan quyidagi jihatlari bilan farq qiladi:

a) fonetik jihatdan-yani ayrim tovushlarning talaffuzi jihatidan. Masalan: katta-kotta, aka-oka (Farg'ona-Toshkent) shevalari.

b) grammatik jihatdan-yani grammatik shakllar, qo'shimchalarni qo'llash jihatidan. Masalan: kelyapti-kelopty (Buxoro-Samarqand) shevasi.

d) leksik jihatdan, ya'ni so'zlarni qo'llash jihatidan. Masalan: narvon-shoti (Andijon) shevasida

O'zbek shevashunoslik fanining ma'lumotiga ko'ra, o'zbek sheva va lahjalari

3 guruhga bo'linadi:

a) janubi-sharqiy guruh: qarluq-chigil-uyg'ur shevalari. Bunga ko'pchilik shahar shevalari kiradi.

b) janubi-g'arbiy guruh: o'g'uz shevalari – Xorazm va Qozog'izton, Turkmanistondagi ba'zi o'zbek shevalari

d) shimoli-g'arbiy guruh: bular qipchoq shevalari nomi bilan yuritiladi.

4. Paremiologiya. Ikki va undan ortiq so'zlarning o'zaro barqaror munosabatidan tashkil topgan, nutq jarayoniga tayyor holda olib kiriluvchi, til egalari xotirasida imkoniyat sifatida mavjud bo'lgan til birliklari barqaror birikmalar deyiladi. Barqaror birikmalarni o'rganuvchi tilshunoslik bo'limi paremiologiya barqaror birikmalar lug'atini tuzish muammolarini o'rganuvchi bo'lim esa paremiografiya sanaladi. Barqaror birikmalar nutqqa tayyor holda olib kirilishi, tarkibiy qismlarning barqarorligi belgisiga ko'ra umumiylikni tashkil etsa ham, ma'no butunligi nuqtayi nazaridan turlichadir. Shunga ko'ra barqaror birikmalar quyidagi guruhlarga bo'linadi:

a) frazeologizmlar b) maqol va matallar

d) aforizmlar (hikmatli so'zlar).

5. Frazeologiya. Tilshunoslikning kichik sohasi bo'lib, fraza – ibora, logos – ta'limot deganidir. Bu bo'limda iboralar (turg'un birikmalar, frazeologik birikmalar, frazeologizmlar) o'rganiladi. Iboralarga xos asosiy xususiyatlar quyidagilardan iborat:

- ibora ikki yoki undan ortiq so'zdan iborat bo'ladi;

- ibora tarkibidagi so'zlar lug'aviy ma'nosini yaxlitligicha ko'chma ma'no ifodalaydi;

- ibora so'z va qo'shma so'zlar singari tayyor material, lug'aviy birlik, til hodisasi hisoblanadi.

Demak, iboralar nutqqa tayyor holda olib kiriladi;

- ibora tarkibidagi so'zlar nutqiy jarayonga qadar barqaror munosabatga kirishgan bo'ladi;

- ibora tarkibidagi soʻzlar orasida sintaktik aloqa boʻlmaydi;

- iboralar mazmuniy yaxlitlikka ega boʻladi, koʻpincha mazmunan bir leksemaga teng keladi.

Iboralar soʻzlar singari omonimlik, antonimlik, sinonimlik xususiyatga ega.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og’ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from

<http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

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